

D4.1

Review of methodologies for cost benefit analysis and internalizing externalities for sustainability certification

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ABBREVIATIONS

CBA	Cost benefit analysis
LCA	Life cycle analysis
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
RVO	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (Rijksdienst Voor Ondernemend)
TEEB	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the results of Task 4.1, which is a part of Work Package 4 called “Cost and feasibility assessment”. The aim of this study is to provide an inventory of relevant methodologies to assess cost and benefit analysis (CBA) including internalizing externalities. To achieve this aim, firstly a quick review of the literature on CBAs is performed associated with sustainability certifications and their applications. The next step was to explore the recent methodological developments on internalizing externalities for integrating them into the CBA. By combining the information gathered from both steps, a methodology for conducting CBA was proposed, which would be used in Task 4.5 to conduct CBA for the selected biobased value chains.

Section 2 discusses approaches found in literature to assess costs and benefits of sustainability certification. CBA is a systematic process for comparing the benefits and costs of a given decision, and it involves assigning a monetary value to all the activities performed. The aim of CBA is to determine whether the expected benefits of a decision are higher than the expected costs. Sustainability certification schemes are set up and managed by non-public organizations and are designed to enable companies to declare their commitment to environmental quality, social equity, and economic prosperity. The schemes cover the full value chain, from raw material production to market distribution, and they are split up into various principles or main topics. The compliance commitments are built to a large extent on extending the economic value of the product with an environmental and/or social value. Two methodologies are found in the literature that address costs and benefits of certifications at value chain level, namely:

- Methodology RVO (Van Dam et al., 2012): Selecting a biomass certification system – a benchmark on level of assurance, costs and benefits.
- Methodology UNEP (2016): A Guide for the Assessment of the Costs and Benefits of Sustainability Certification.

These studies are further enhanced with additional literature covering certification costs and/or benefits. These costs and benefit are further described in Sections 2.2 and 2.3, where the types of costs and benefits of certification are introduced, and the nature and definition of these items are explained.

In general certification costs and benefits are divided into direct and indirect costs and benefits.

Direct costs are those that are directly related to obtaining and maintaining certification and include certification fees and audit costs. Indirect costs are those that a company incurs to meet the requirements of the certification standards. These costs include upgrading facilities, implementing new management practices, and providing training to employees.

Direct benefits of certification are those benefits that are directly related to obtaining and maintaining certification and include benefits such as efficiency and/or management improvements within company and/or price premium. Indirect benefits of certification are those benefits that are not directly related to obtaining and maintaining certification but are still gained as a result of the certification process (e.g., improved market position, through image, branding and legal compliance).

Overall, the costs of sustainability certification can vary widely depending on the certification scheme and the company seeking certification. However, it is important to note that the benefits of sustainability certification can often outweigh the costs in the long term, as the certification can lead to increased market access, higher prices for certified products, and improved environmental and social outcomes.

Section 3 discusses the concept of internalization of externalities, which refers to measures that ensure external costs or benefits are considered in the composition of prices of goods and services. Externalities can be positive or negative and can be divided into environmental and social categories. Environmental externalities relate to the consequences of production and consumption of a product on the environment and indirectly on people and communities, while social externalities relate to the consequences on people and communities caused by production and consumption of a product. Monetization of externalities involves the valuation of externalities in monetary terms to allow them to be considered in decision-making. Section 3 also highlights the importance of internalizing externalities for establishing sustainable models and discusses different ways to achieve internalization, such as charging polluters with the costs of pollution or implementing certification schemes to achieve internalization by providing more stringent requirements on the production process and ensuring that externalities are reduced. This section also discusses the steps to identify, quantify, and monetize externalities, including using a life cycle assessment (LCA) to measure the impacts on the environment associated with the life cycle of a product, process, or service.

Section 4 discusses alignment between the costs and benefits of certification with internalization of external costs and benefits and monetization, specifically in relation to bio-based value chains and with the practice of certification bodies. The UNEP and RVO method for sustainability certification do not include externalities in their methodology, thus Section 4 extends their methods by incorporating external costs and benefits into cost and benefit of certification schemes. Table 7 presents the extended version of the costs and benefits of certification schemes, including internalized externalities, and outlines possible sources of evidence for the following up data collection process (to be executed in the Tasks 4.3-4.4).

Section 5 provides conclusions and discussion on the methodological challenges. Generally, the literature review highlights some methodological challenges in conducting a cost-benefit analysis of certification schemes. While there are several studies that identify the effects of certification schemes, there are too few studies that value such effects. The complexity of the evaluation and monetization of the impacts is also a significant challenge.

One specific challenge is the quantification of costs, especially audit costs, which are case-study specific and depend on various factors. The literature also suggests that forestry and agro-food sectors have been studied more frequently than other sectors, so the sector coverage may be a challenging aspect when addressing other sectors and products. Finding the right data, especially those related to external costs and benefits, is expected to be very difficult. Studies on the level of assurance of certification schemes and the external drivers of certification adoption or barriers to its adoption can be useful in dealing with this challenge. The assumption here is that it is rather costly to adopt certification schemes for cases when barriers of adoption are faced. Thus, it is important to consider both the internal and external success factors of certification schemes when quantifying the costs and benefits. Additionally, it is important to consider the challenges faced by small-scale companies when adopting certification schemes, such as lack of resources, competence, and appropriate environmental management schemes. These challenges can increase the costs of adopting certification schemes for small-scale companies and need to be taken into consideration when quantifying the costs and benefits of certification schemes.

In conclusion, while there are challenges in conducting a cost-benefit analysis of certification schemes, the findings from the literature and practice can provide valuable insights for the data collection process and the preparation of the data collection template. Having outlined the methodology and the main challenges to address, Section 6 offers the next steps to be taken towards costs-benefit analysis of selected bio-based value chains. These are mainly selection of bio-based value chains and certification schemes (Task 4.2), development of data collection template (Task

4.3), performing data collection for the three selected bio-based value chains (Task 4.4) and carrying out CBA (Task 4.5).

1. Introduction

This task (T4.1) aims to provide an inventory of relevant methodologies to assess cost and benefit analysis (CBA) including internalizing externalities. For this purpose, firstly, a quick scan of literature on CBA of sustainability certification and its applications is performed to identify the relevant cost and benefit items. Next, to incorporate the externalities in the CBA, a literature review on the recent methodological developments on internalizing externalities is carried out. In this project, we refer to the definition of The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB). TEEB (2018) defines externalities¹ as the positive or negative consequences of an economic activity or transaction that affect other parties without this being reflected in the price of the goods or services transacted. The literature review on internalization of externalities provides information on the type of data to be collected prior of doing the monetisation of impacts and contributes to better understanding of how the monetisation is performed for environmental and social impacts. The synthesis of the learnings from both these steps results in the proposed methodology for CBA to be applied in Task 4.5 to carry out CBA for the selected biobased value chains.

1.1 Approach

The research questions addressed in this report are the following:

- How can the CBA method of sustainability certification be adapted to assess certification in biobased value chains?
- What are the data needs to estimate investment and operating costs, added benefits, and avoided costs as specified in existing methodologies?

A literature review is performed in two streams. The literature around costs and benefits of certification schemes is consulted (see Section 2), as well as the literature on externalities and monetisation of externalities is consulted in parallel (see Section 3). The purpose of the literature review in the first instance was to identify if additional methodologies, next to the “UNEP Guide for the Assessment of the Costs and Benefits of Sustainability Certification” which was identified during the proposal preparation (UNEP, 2016), are available. We used search engines like google, google scholar, ScienceDirect and consulted scientific literature and grey literature, as well as the Evidensia database (www.evidensia.eco). For the review on certification schemes and their costs and benefits, the search terms were “certification schemes”, “sustainability standards”, “sustainability certification”, “certification cost-benefit”, “costs certification”, “benefits certification”, “externalities”, “internalization”, “monetisation”, “life cycle analysis”, all in combination with bio-based products. The learning point was to use the names of the bio-based certification schemes and bio-based products to get more detail analysis on specific cost/benefit items. We also used a snowballing using the UNEP reference as the key document. The screening of the literature provides information on the type of data to be collected prior to doing the monetisation of externalities. This report provides guiding principles of performing a cost-benefit analysis of a selected value chain that has adopted a certain sustainability certification scheme (level of a company that applies for a certification, i.e., a case-study). In particular, it provides a detailed description of specific costs and benefit items that need to be taken into account for evaluation of the adoption of sustainable certification schemes in biobased value chains.

¹ In this document, the terms externalities and external costs/benefits are both used interchangeably, since they originate in different flows of literature, with externalities adding on to internal costs and benefits. Positive externalities are similar to external benefits, whereas negative externalities are similar to external costs.

1.2 Reader guide

This document consists of three parts. The first two parts present the methodological considerations that are to be considered when proceeding with cost-benefit analysis in Task 4.5 of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. The first part addresses the costs and benefits of certification that are identified from literature review. The second part describes externalities and discusses the monetization of these externalities. Part three combines the learnings from the previous parts. Then adapts the methodologies specifically to the costs-benefit analysis of sustainability certification in bio-based value chains and elaborates on externalities that occur during (sustainability) certification. Part three also builds on the learnings derived from the work on typology of bio-based products (D1.1 “Classification of biological resources and biobased products”), typology of certification schemes (D1.2 “Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels”) and on representative bio-based value chains (D2.1 “Identification of the most representative biobased value chains”) and gained from collaborative discussions with the sister projects HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS that address the call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: International and European sustainability certification schemes of bio-based systems.

2. Approaches to assess costs and benefits of sustainability certification

This section describes the approaches used in literature to assess the costs and benefits of sustainable certification scheme and starts with a description of a general cost-benefit-analysis in Section 2.1. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 are devoted to a detailed description of costs and benefits of (sustainability) certification and their driving factors respectively. Section 2.4 presents findings from literature on effectiveness of certification schemes on costs and benefits.

2.1 Cost-benefit-analysis in a nutshell

A cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a systematic process for calculating and comparing benefits and costs of a given decision, and it is based on assigning a monetary value to all the activities performed (either as input or output). Given a set of options, a decision (e.g., adoption of a certification scheme) should be undertaken if the expected benefit is higher than the expected costs of the project.

CBA is grounded in welfare economics. CBA is based on a social welfare function, which aggregates the welfare of individuals to obtain an expression for the welfare of society as a whole (Renes & Romijn, 2013). The welfare changes caused by measures are expressed through the willingness of people to pay for the effects of the measures. Willingness to pay is an indication of the value someone puts on the services or goods directly or indirectly generated by the proposed project or policy measures. If the costs of the measure are lower than the willingness to pay for the effects, the measure increases welfare. Conversely, if the costs are higher than the willingness to pay it reduces welfare. CBA uses a broad concept of welfare which includes things that people value, but are not traded on markets, such as environmental quality, health and safety. These are things that people not only attribute a positive value to, but which they also pay for, either directly or via the government.

A CBA is an information tool that provides an overview of the economic effects of a measure and the resulting costs and benefits to the society as a whole. Renes and Romijn (2013) developed a CBA methodology “General Guidance for Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)”, which describes how to make the analysis generally suitable for a variety of measures in all policy fields. By quantifying advantages and disadvantages of a measure to the society and assigning monetary values to them (costs/benefits), CBA provides insights in the social-welfare effects of the measure expressed as the

balance in euros of the benefits minus the costs. There is no watertight definition of the difference between costs of a measure and the negative benefits. However, it makes no difference in welfare economics how we define costs. As long as all the positive and negative welfare effects have been accounted for, the balance will be calculated correctly and it does not matter what parts of the effects have been included under the costs (Renes & Romijn, 2013).

Before diving into costs and benefits of sustainability certifications schemes there is a need to describe what sustainability certification schemes provide, and how this actually works in practice. This information can be found in the Section 2.1.1 followed by a section 2.1.2 on costs and benefits of certification schemes.

2.1.1 Sustainability certification in a nutshell

Sustainability schemes are mostly set up and managed by non-public organisations, supported by, and supporting either a broad range of products, or as specific industry or sector, thereby enabling the certified companies to declare their commitment to environmental quality, social equity, and economic prosperity. The compliance commitments are built to a large extent on extending economic value of the product with an environmental and/or social value, that are split up in various principles, or main topics the scheme is covering. In almost all cases, these schemes cover the full value chain, from raw material production to collecting, trading, processing, and market distribution, often referred to as supply chain elements. It is therefore important that the sustainability principles are addressed to the right supply chain element, as not all principles may apply to all companies involved in the supply chain. As an example: sustainable land use (with the requirement of protecting high carbon stock) could be a principle of a scheme, which shall be addressed at the raw material production element of the value chain. A processing facility further downstream will not need to be audited against that principle. However, a processing facility looking to get certified, shall have to provide proof that it received raw material from a supplier that was audited against that principle. This is normally assured by requiring that all companies in a value chain that hold ownership on the material are certified against the applicable certification scheme criteria. This is generally referred to as “chain of custody” certification. Only those materials purchased from a certified supplier and with the certified claim, can be considered compliant with the scheme requirements and be sold further into the certified value chain (either with or without processing it). The chain of custody criteria shall therefore apply to all value chain elements.

Another example of a principle could be related to the working conditions of employees of the companies in the certified value chain (for example related to protecting workers against forced labour or child labour). Here it also makes sense to audit against that principle at the raw material production, but in this case these risks may also occur at processing sites, depending on the type of processing that is applied. So that principle may be connected to multiple value chain elements, but most likely not to all of them (as it would not affect companies that solely trade material, for example). The knowledge on the number of actors across the value chain involved into the process of certification may also be guiding when assessing the costs as well as benefits. For example, Better Biomass scheme (NEN, 2018) stipulates which actors need to comply with each of the criteria of this certification scheme.

Deliverable 1.2 “Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels” is a useful document that illustrates a large variety of standards and certification schemes applicable to bio-based products. Compliance criteria and principles are not only important structures within each standard or certification scheme but can also be used in assessing indicative costs and benefits. Overview of criteria across standards and their mapping along groupings can be useful in understanding the potential complexity of each standard and thus their costs and benefits. The “ITC Standards Map”

that is also considered in Deliverable 1.2 enables for comparison of standards/ certification schemes along performance criteria as grouping: environmental, social, management and ethical, quality, operational. The “ITC Standards Map” is helpful in deploying the specific sub-groups of requirements like Human rights, Labour rights, Local communities (all within social performance), and the underlying indicators, that represent each sub-group. Requirements and the indicators that represent the requirements can be helpful in a more granular literature investigation in search for indication on costs and benefits.

2.1.2 Costs and benefits of certification

Two methodologies are found in the literature that address costs and benefits of certifications at value chain level, namely:

- Methodology RVO (Van Dam et al., 2012): Selecting a biomass certification system – a benchmark on level of assurance, costs and benefits.
- Methodology UNEP (2016): A Guide for the Assessment of the Costs and Benefits of Sustainability Certification.

The method developed by CPB and PBL (see Renes and Romijn (2013)), discussed earlier in Section 2.1, is specifically designed for policy measures, while the methodology of UNEP and RVO are designed for certification schemes. There is also a study on company certification (set of ISO 14100 standard) by Camilleri (2022), however its level of application is different from the desired value-chain level. Nevertheless, these two additional references are also of interest for the overall methodology CBA.

Differences are observed in the types of costs that are considered in RVO and UNEP methodologies. This is due to the difference in the perspective/scope taken by each of them. While RVO methodology has a producer/company perspective (i.e., for assessing costs and benefits of certification experienced by a company and its direct surroundings), UNEP methodology takes a public sector perspective that is very extensive and provides detailed coverage of costs and benefits (expanding on the boundaries of different actors, contributing to the functionality of the certification as a co-regulation instrument). RVO methodology is focusing on certification for biofuels, while UNEP methodology relates to the sectors of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries.

Table 1 presents a concise overview of the costs and benefits items described in the RVO and UNEP methodologies. These costs and benefit are further described in Sections 2.2 and 2.3, where the types of costs and benefits of certification are introduced, and the nature and definition of these items are explained. Also, costs and benefits that are found in the literature in addition to those in Table 1 are also added. Each of the cost components in Table 1 contains a number of sub-items that are all spelled out below. All costs and benefits are identified for the case of private (internal to the company) and public (external to the company) aspects. Public costs and benefits are to be assessed at social and environmental dimensions. From a private sector perspective, costs related to sustainability compliance refer to the costs for improving the sustainability of production (e.g., the purchase of machinery and the transformation of production processes and techniques, potential additional labour, and training costs), called indirect costs.

From a public sector point of view, public costs refer to the allocation and/or reallocation of financial resources with the aim to create enabling conditions for the development of sustainable businesses in a given country.

Table 1 Private (internal) costs and benefits in a nutshell

Item	Cost typology	Item/short explanation
Costs	Direct costs	Auditing costs
		Certification fees
	Indirect costs	Administrative indirect costs, including training costs to prepare for audits Indirect costs related to sustainability compliance (including upgrading of facilities, training costs related to introducing better production practices to adhere to standards)
Benefits	Direct benefits	Efficiency and/or management improvements within company (e.g. benefits related to reduction in the use of inputs, such as water, fertilizers and energy)
		Price premium
	Indirect benefits	Improved market position (image, branding and legal compliance)

Source: own presentation, based on RVO (2012) and UNEP (2016). Further explanation is provided in Section 4.

In addition to *economic* returns deriving from market dynamics, the CBA of sustainability certification should include an estimation of *social benefits* generated (UNEP, 2016). Following UNEP (2016), sustainable production practices generally require more labour force to be carried. As a result, additional employment and income opportunities might be created due to the certification, as well as new jobs could be created from the establishment of new value chains, with greater advantages potentially accruing to poor communities in developing countries.

Indirect costs depend on the sustainability requirements of a system (how many, level of strictness) are also largely influenced by the preparedness of a company to meet the requirements Van Dam et al. (2012).

Following UNEP (2016) methodology, which takes the perspective of a social sector, quickly leads to the conclusion that the cost items that are presented in this framework are even more difficult to estimate than costs at the company level. The methodology of UNEP, next to an estimation of social benefits also require inclusion of environmental benefits. Environmental benefits can be derived from sustainability certification schemes due to the preservation of natural capital. For example, the valorisation of native forests and their biological products is expected to improve the provision of other forest goods and services, watershed preservation and carbon sequestration services, among others. Moreover, the environmental benefits of healthier ecosystems would be enjoyed across key sectors, such as water management (e.g., through watershed preservation and better conservation of water resources in protected areas) and agriculture (higher soil quality). As a result, relevant national and international studies and data could be used to estimate the economic value of added environmental benefits derived from sustainability certification investments (UNEP, 2016).

2.2 Costs of (sustainability) certification and their driving factors

In this section we zoom into direct and indirect costs of sustainability certification that were listed in Table 1 and present some examples.

Certification fees (e.g., direct costs) for a system can be split into two components, a registration/certificate fee and / or a quantity-dependent fee. In that way they generate revenues in such a way that all contribute, but those who use the scheme most (and benefit most) also contribute accordingly. Some systems require registration with the scheme to access a part of the

documentation and being able to start the certification process. Most of the schemes are governed through an association, that gives companies and other stakeholders the opportunity to become a member, as a way to show commitment and to have a say in the governance and decision-making process of the scheme. Membership fees are generally based on property sizes, amount of feedstock processed or yearly financial turnovers.

The certification schemes are also explicit on the direct costs. For the case of FSC, see FSC (2022), the detailing of costs goes to the level of detail when the dates of invoicing are specified (4 times per year). Next, the fees will depend on the type of resource and in the case of FSC, different type of forest management categories also show differentiation in fees. Natural Forest for Conservation purposes would rate USD 0.0001/ha while plantations would be charged 20 times more at USD 0.0020/ha.

Table 2 provides some examples of the selected certification schemes. The costs vary greatly between different schemes, covering different sectors.

Table 2 Example of costs applied by selected certification schemes.

Cost items / Certification scheme and source	RSB (RSB, 2022a) and (RSB, 2022b)	RSPO (2022)	ISCC (2022)
Annual membership fee	375-30.000 US\$	Regular: 2000€ Small: 500€ Affiliate: 250€ Associate: 100€	Companies: 500-3000€
Certification fee	One time registration: (500US\$)	n.a.	Certification fee (based on turnover) 200-2000 €
Quantity dependent fee	For feedstock producer (based on hectare cultivation area): maximum (25. 000 US\$ per year) For industrial operators (based on metric tons sold): 0.05% of the price of sold product (range 1.000 – 50.000 US\$ per year) For traders: Independent Trader: US\$1,000 per office and/or site. Traders associated exclusively with production sites: US\$100 per office and/or site.	For feedstock producer: 1.30 US\$ mt (Certified Sustainable Palm Oil) 0.59 US\$ mt (Certified Sustainable Palm Kernel)	Minimum 250 € For First gathering points, individually certified farms, collecting points, individually certified points of origin, central offices, traders, individually certified FPR: 0.01 €/mt For Processing units: 0.10 €/mt ISCC members 20% reduction on total fee

Source: own presentation.

The certification fee also varies with size of the company or with the number of sites certified. This is also called a quantity dependent fee. In most cases, operators are required to pay a fee per metric ton of biomass or biobased product certified. For example, for the ISCC certification (ISCC, 2022), quantity dependent fees start from 250 euro and vary between 1 cent per Mton to 10 cent per Mton

(see Table 2). For the same certification scheme, the membership fees for companies vary from 500 euro /year to 3000 euro/year, depending on the company size.

Auditing costs include the costs that a company must pay for an external audit to become or remain certified. Covered in these costs are preparation, field audit and reporting costs. Different types of information requirements and audit procedures determine the direct costs of certification. Auditing costs are usually reflected by man-days needed to perform an audit. The day tariff for an audit is a market price that varies between countries and certification bodies. The day tariff for an audit can also be affected by the selection of a certification system. In case the certification body needs to invest more in training and competencies of auditors, that may be reflected in the day tariff. The number of days of an audit, however, does depend on the selected system and on the scope of the company (e.g., an FGP requires more audit days than a trading company).

Bok et al. (2022) present the audit costs for the MSPO scheme (The Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil Scheme), differentiating between types of tariffs and activities. Day tariffs and subsistence costs, number on-site visits including stakeholder consultation and certification and surveillance types of audits are differentiated. Each certification scheme will have more or less the same costs items and differentiate, depending on the nature of the feedstock / biobased material. Few examples of the certification audit fees from Van Dam et al. (2012) are provided in Annex (Table A. 1 for the auditing fees and Table A. 3Table A. 2 for the auditing days).

Following Van Dam et al. (2012), factors that may increase the number of days for an audit, *independent of the system*, are:

- Difficult access to the location (travel days)
- Size of the company (e.g., number of storage facilities, distance between units)
- Complexity of the company
- Total number of producers in the group
- Actions in a new country/region

Factors that may increase the number of days for an audit, *dependent of the system*, are Van Dam et al. (2012):

- Difficult stakeholder context (affects the success of the stakeholder consultations)
- Large subcontracted labour
- Significant number of complaints/non-compliances
- Sampling requirements by the system
- Documentation requirements (detail of forms, amounts of forms, information to be checked)
- Scope and verification requirements for sustainability principles

2.3 Benefits of (sustainability) certification and their driving factors

Following RVO methodology (Van Dam et al., 2012), certification may generate a number of benefits for adopters. Two types of benefits can be distinguished: internal company benefits and external benefits. Selecting the most suitable certification system could result in better cost or profit margins for a company, this depending on the type of benefit. Table 3 is adopted from RVO methodology and although this study was done for biofuel value chain and in this project, we focus on biobased

products value chain, it serves as a good starting point. The table indicates the types of benefits and the recipients of these benefits. Recent literature search confirms the types of benefits as listed in RVO methodology and adds few more.

Table 3 Indication of recipients of benefits for certification along the supply chain

Type of benefit	Recipient
Efficiency and management improvements	Requirements on this aspect are laid down in the producer standard: Benefits mostly at <u>farm level</u>
Meeting demands of the market	Relevant for <u>all actors</u> in the supply chain
Legal compliance producer country	Requirements on legal compliance are laid down in the producer standard: Direct benefits at <u>farm level</u> though <u>other actors</u> also benefit from this assurance in terms of risk management
Image and branding	For those companies that want to distinguish their product from other market players; mostly relevant to larger companies or <u>end-users in the market.</u>
Price premium	At the point where there is a demand and / or shortage for a specific certified intermediate or end product – more likely to be at the end of the value chain (<u>traders, biofuel producers</u>)
Legal compliance producer country	Requirements on legal compliance are laid down in the producer standard: Direct benefits at <u>farm level</u> though <u>other actors</u> also benefit from this assurance in terms of risk management

Source: adopted from Van Dam et al. (2012).

Internal company benefits refer to management or efficiency improvements within a company, which may lead to better cost-margins. Various systems have integrated this economic principle in their standard.

Companies can select between product certification or company certification. The sustainability certification of industrial bio-based value chain refers to certification schemes per product. Companies who are profiling as guides in certification for business companies (both, per company or per product) and thus like to engage more firms into certification schemes (see Zujewski (2021)), state the benefits of sustainability certification as following:

- Certification drives executive and employee involvement and alignment
- Certification drives employee engagement and creates a sustainable culture
- Sustainable business certification drives profit.

Recent study by the European Commission (2021) on bio-based plastics investigated the benefits of certification in bio-based plastics. Next to the benefits in Table 3, the following can be added:

- Risk management.
- Market access and growth
- Company commitment.

The positive impact of certification on company performance is observed in the literature. Based on an analysis of more than 200 different sources, Clark et al. (2014) found that 88% of companies with solid sustainability practices had better operational performance. The direction of the causality here may be questioned, i.e., whether not the companies with advanced performance did put forward their engagement with certification schemes, but this is not crucial to understand for the question at hand.

Following Van Dam et al. (2012), benefits are interrelated and will finally all influence the price that will be paid on the market for a product: A positive image and demand (or shortage) on the market for a product will increase price levels. Efficiency improvements will reduce costs. At the end, it is relevant to evaluate in how far benefits outweigh the costs for certification. Also, it is important to know which actors in the supply chain profit the most from these benefits. This information provides insight into the final burden (or benefit) of certification to the market.

The ISEAL study on business benefits of adopting of sustainability standards (Molenaar, 2022) proposes a framework for such benefits. Table A. 3 in Annex provides a list of early benefits and their and end benefits. Following this study, early benefits that businesses can realise from the adoption of sustainability standards are linked to business operations, procurement, marketing and sales, stakeholder engagement and driving sector-wide change. Adopting standards can be seen as a long-term asset in which the return on investment only becomes clear after some time. Within these final benefits, the ISEAL report distinguishes between benefits supporting business value and benefits contributing to sustainability impact. The first category refers to final benefits that improve the financial return on investment of the business itself. It includes aspects of profit, productivity/sales and reputation. The second category, sustainability impact, refers to the social return on investment of using standards in terms of social, environmental, and economic impacts. The ISEAL report encourages the research community to do more research on the value of the production and trade of sustainable products for all business along the value chain, instead of focusing on the benefits for upstream actors and particularly producers. This review included some interesting examples of cost-benefit analysis of the use of sustainability standards, including some looking at both tangible and intangible benefits. This is a positive development, though they mainly looked at these benefits for producers, not on the rest of the value chain.

Based on the proportion of sources that refer to the benefit, the study concludes that operational benefits (human capital development, sustainability strategy, operational efficiency) were most frequently referenced (83%), followed by benefits related to sales and marketing (like price premium, market access, marketing strategy). Benefits linked to human capital refers to benefits related to improved working conditions and worker benefits, employee skill development and improved employee satisfaction and retention within the business.

Also in the study by Wolff and Schweinle (2022) economic benefits are mentioned as the most frequently explored drivers of certification. This review study investigated effectiveness and economic viability of forest certification. Multiple indicators (price premiums, cost-benefit ratios, revenues and sales, profitability, household income) were studied in the context of economic viability, not always providing a complete picture of the economic impacts of certification over time. An explanation of this scattered evidence may derive from the fact that some forest managers were not fully aware of the financial costs and benefits of certification, sometimes due to indirect benefits

perceived as necessary for having a potential long-term economic effect (e.g., improved market access). In addition, following the review of Wolff and Schweinle (2022) some studies indicated that cost data was treated confidentially and as proprietary or was not fully reported and that only a few studies measured and reported the costs of forest certification based on actual organizational data. Figure 1 presents the impact of forest certification on economic viability, presented by indicator and number of case studies.

Figure 1 Impact of forest certification on economic viability of certified businesses, presented by five indicators and the number of case studies.

Source: Wolff and Schweinle (2022).

The studies reviewed by Malek and Abdul Rahim (2022) for the case of forestry certification show evidence for various types of benefits, both economic and social, and can be consulted for further exploration. Forest certification is widely regarded as one of the most useful tools for achieving sustainable forest management, promoting the sustainable utilisation of forest resources, and improving the company’s brand and image. Additionally, businesses adopt voluntary forest certification schemes for economic benefit. This is supported by several articles covered in the review by Malek and Abdul Rahim (2022) that demonstrate how landowners seek forest certification to gain an advantage in terms of expanded market access, especially to environmentally sensitive external markets. Landowners also benefit from gaining price premiums for certified products and increased profits. In other words, firms involved in forest certification are seeking to gain a competitive advantage.

While the work by Van Dam et al. (2012), which is very relevant for this methodology, already mentions these types of benefits, it does not address the employee engagement into sustainability pathways through certification, while more studies address these social aspects. Regarding the forest certification, the review study by Van Dam et al. (2012) has also looked into the motivation for participating in forest certification by timber chain players (forest owners, timber industries, state administrations or nongovernmental organisations (NGOs). Studies document that forest certification can be adopted at the state level to improve forest management practices, while NGOs regard it as an important tool for preserving social development and resolving environmental issues. Multiple references are found regarding the motivation of forest owners and timber industries to adopt forest certification as a tool for improving forest management practices promoting the sustainable utilisation of forest resources and improving the company’s brand and image, in overall gaining a competitive advantage. Most studies address the primary production of the chains.

2.4 Discussion on findings from studies on certification schemes

As the number of studies on the effectiveness of certification, including its costs and benefits, grows, so does the number of (systematic) review studies that are listed in this section. There are many studies that identify costs and benefits of certification schemes. Regarding the costs, some studies call it investments and not costs, or call it “negative outcomes”. Regarding the benefits, some studies address impacts, effectiveness, and efficacy of certification or speak about “positive outcomes” of certification or their advantages. Only few studies deal with cost-benefit analysis as such, i.e. by relating the cost to the benefits and deriving net results. This is also confirmed in the ISEAL study (Molenaar, 2022). That provides a framework for business benefits of certifications. Also, what concerns the UNEP (2016) methodology only few studies have applied it and yet to a limited extent. Namely, none of the studies that applied the UNEP methodology have been able to fully quantify all costs and benefits as the methodology suggests. Instead, the studies named the costs and benefits without quantifying these (see UNEP, 2015).

Studies evaluating costs and benefits of voluntary agricultural certification are increasing (Traldi, 2021). However, most studies do not address all sustainability pillars. While there is evidence around trade-offs between socioeconomic and environmental outcomes, these trade-offs are not investigated thereby resulting in an incomplete picture of the benefits and challenges of certification. Among reviewed studies by Traldi (2021) on the effects of voluntary agricultural certification, results tended to be positive (51%), followed by no difference (41%). As concluded by Wolff and Schweinle (2022), different factors contribute to the effectiveness of forest certification. These include the stringency of standards, certification uptake, patterns of adoption, compliance and enforcement of standards, and the long-term direct and indirect effects of certification. These factors are closely linked to the local context in which certification is applied, affecting the outcome of the intervention and changes over time. Additionally, market structures and access to capital determine the economic viability of forest certification and can impact whether differences between countries can be detected or not. For the more specific case of the forest certification, the review study by Malek and Abdul Rahim (2022) has documented what studies report on the types of benefits of forest certification. These are:

- The certification has allowed access to new markets linked to increases in sales volume and timber prices;
- The certification has helped develop a niche market for businesses;
- The certification has resulted in increased revenue by product branding, acquiring customers’ trust and extensive product marketing.
- Additionally, forest certification effectively addresses social and labour issues, such as worker rights, occupational safety and health of workers, firm relationships, and consultation with local communities, as well as the living and working conditions of workers and their families.

Regarding the coverage of sectors and products, Tröster and Hiete (2018) confirm that the majority of studies that addresses challenges of certification schemes are in the forestry, agro-food and marine sectors. The authors clarify this through the long history of such schemes: the oldest and most widely studied certification schemes stem from these sectors. Thus, the schemes that prevail in these sectors are studied: in the forestry sector the FSC and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Schemes (PEFC); for the agro-food sector these are Fairtrade, different organic certifications (Organic) and the Rainforest Alliance (RA); and for the marine sector - the

Marine Stewardship Council (MSC). For non-agro-food sectors, the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED), were often examined (sector of building). Other schemes are not prominently referenced in the review studies. Also in Traldi (2021) the key research gap is indicated in an underrepresentation of studies for certain crops, certifications, and regions. Although there is a growing evidence base, it is still unbalanced. For example, over 80% of the studies included in the review by DeFries et al. (2017) were focused on coffee certification. Similar observation is done in the review of Jellema et al. (2022): impact of certification is mostly studied in the context of certification standards related to a limited number of commodity sectors like coffee (27%), forestry (13%), and fishery (10%), i.e. the sectors with certifications being the most prominent.

Regarding the geographical representation, several review studies confirm that most publications are conducted in Europe, Asia, and South America (Wolff & Schweinle, 2022). In terms of scope presented, Jellema et al. (2022) concludes that most of the impact-related work on certification had a micro focus, with half of the studies conducted in the context of one specific geographic location (50%) and the majority focused on one specific moment in time (66%). Also, the authors conclude that more evidence is needed from other chain partners (or stakeholder groups) than farmers.

Some authors acknowledge the weaknesses of the national statistics which exhibit difficulty of distinguishing between bio-based and non-bio-based products. This bottleneck complicates the analysis of impacts of bio-based certification (see Jander et al. (2020) and Morone et al. (2021)) and may appear in the follow up work on the application of our methodology.

Most of the systematic review studies have been found for the forestry certification schemes. There are multiple studies that analyse costs, impacts, challenges of measuring impacts, drivers of forestry FSC certification in different countries. The systematic review articles like those in Wolff and Schweinle (2022), Malek and Abdul Rahim (2022) and Tröster and Hiete (2018) provide enough examples of such cases. These are useful for the CBA methodology when specific value chains are to be assessed for a specific product and certification category. The review studies are available for the forestry and agricultural products certification schemes. However, studies for the sectors of cosmetics, textile or plastic have not been yet extensively searched for and have not appeared in generic searches on certification schemes. Thus, finding the right data may become a challenge when doing a CBA for the value chains in these sectors.

Thus, when studying impacts of certification in bio-based value chains, the literature search should focus either on specific certification schemes or on specific products. However, the findings for sectors other than agriculture, forestry and fishery might be extremely limited.

There is a possibility to quantify costs and benefits through the relation with factors that may influence these, described in sections 2.2 and 2.3. Already in Van Dam et al. (2012) the relationship between costs/benefits and the level of certification assurance is mentioned. Also, the relationship between external factors of the certification adoption and the costs/benefits can be found.

The RVO methodology presents the following relationship depicted in Table 4. These can be guiding in cost-benefit assessments.

Table 4 Relation between cost – benefits and level of assurance and key influencing factors

	Relation with level of assurance	External factors
Costs	Stakeholder consultation Coverage sustainability standard Strictness sustainability standard Sampling requirements	System structure Annual turn over Size company Location company

	Type of auditing required Traceability tools	Complexity product
Benefits	Internal benefit: Efficiency improvements Management improvements	Market demand Shortage in market Policy driven Competition

Source: Van Dam et al. (2012).

Further search for the literature on the relationship between success and barriers of adoption of voluntary sustainability certification schemes may be helpful in quantifying the costs. The assumption here is that it is rather costly to adopt certification schemes for cases when barriers of adoption are faced. The initial literature search has identified a systematic literature review that was conducted by Tröster and Hiete (2018). The authors focused on success factors and success dimensions of voluntary sustainability certification schemes across different sectors allowed the authors to develop a framework explaining generic factors for the success of certification schemes. The success factors of certification schemes are identified along external and internal dimensions. Among the internal success factors the following are mentioned: stakeholder involvement, quality of requirements, capacity building, quality of audits, transparency of certification schemes (which is similar to the level of assurance as identified in Table 4). Governmental influences, characteristics of the adopting entity are mentioned among the external success factors. In a similar type of review but focused on small-scale companies, Flagstad et al. (2022) refer to the challenges related to environmental certification in such companies that seem well-established in the literature. These include lack of resources, competence, and appropriate environmental management schemes. Moreover, while large organizations may have the skills and resources to implement all-encompassing environmental certification schemes, these schemes may not be tailored to promote environmental sustainability in small organizations. The authors summarise experiences of the drivers and hindrances in certification processes, that may be of importance in search for new literature on costs and benefits of certification which can be affiliated with drivers and barriers depending on the company characteristics, customers and markets and even emotions. As an example: positive reputation of a company due to gained certification can resonance with greenwashing when such cases become public and discouraging. In case like that, the benefits of certification can be lower opposite to the cases when greenwashing does not or happens to much smaller extent. Table A. 4 in Annex presents drivers and barriers as specified in the review by Flagstad et al. (2022).

3. Literature on internalisation of externalities

3.1 Internalisation of externalities

Externalities can be positive or negative. In case of positive externalities¹, the actions affect the other person's wellbeing in a positive manner (benefit). Conversely, the actions affect the other person's wellbeing in a negative manner (costs) in case of negative externalities. These costs or benefits are external as they are not included in market prices. Therefore, they are also called external costs and external benefits. Internal costs (or benefits) are the costs (benefits) included in market prices. An example of internal costs are the investment costs, operation costs and fuel cost that result from the production of timber and internal benefits are the revenues obtained by selling wood products. Various pollutants are emitted during the production of timber, such as greenhouse gasses, particulate matter and phosphorus, which harm environmental quality and human health (Saosee et al., 2022). These external costs are paid by the society, for instance via medical expenses, accident compensation and taxes (European Commission, 2019).

External costs can become internal by incorporating it into the market decision making process through pricing (e.g. taxation) or regulatory interventions (EEA, 2006). This process is defined as the internalisation of externalities. Hence, internalisation refers to measures that guarantee that external costs or benefits are taken into account in the composition of goods and services prices (Ding et al., 2014). Internalization of externalities can be assessed at different levels: along the value chain, within a company, or in comparison between products (Eidelwein et al., 2018). One way to achieve internalization is by charging polluters with the costs of the pollution generated, which is in accordance with the polluter pays principle (EEA, 2006). Another way to achieve internalization is by implementing a certification scheme in the value chain that is providing more stringent requirements on the production process and thus ensures that externalities are reduced. In this project, certification schemes are considered for the internalization of externalities. By internalizing externalities, agents pay for the costs of generating negative externalities or receive benefits for generating positive externalities. Not including externalities in financial statements prevents the mitigation of these externalities. Furthermore, truly sustainable models cannot be established if these effects are not managed (Ding et al., 2014).

In order to internalize externalities associated with the production and consumption of a product, they should first be identified, quantified and monetized (Eidelwein et al., 2018). These steps are further discussed in the remainder of this subsection.

3.1.1 Identify externalities

Several studies provide a longlist of externalities that might be relevant for assessing the external costs and benefits of products, particularly in the domain of agri-food. See for instance, Woltjer et al. (2021), Galgani et al. (2021) and the True Cost Initiative (2022). Externalities can be divided into two categories: social externalities and environmental externalities. Environmental externalities relate to the consequences of production and consumption of a product on the environment and indirectly on people and communities (see Section 3.3). Social externalities relate to the consequences on people

¹ In this document, the terms externalities and external costs/benefits are both used. Positive externalities are similar to external benefits, whereas negative externalities are similar to external costs.

and communities caused by production and consumption of a product (see Section 3.2). Eidelwein et al. (2018) propose three steps to identify these externalities. First, a diagram of the production process should be designed, which identifies the processes/functional areas and material flows developed within the frontiers delimited for the evaluation. Second, groups of externalities should be identified and recorded. These groups can be for instance air pollution, greenhouse gas emissions and water consumption. Third, the externalities should be identified at an environmental impact level. Galgani et al. (2021) propose a materiality assessment to identify the externalities that are relevant for a case study. A materiality assessment is an evaluation of which externalities are relevant for which products, supply chains, or parts of a supply chain, based on academic literature and expert elicitation.

3.1.2 Quantify externalities

After the externalities are identified, they should be quantified. Environmental externalities are often quantified by using a life cycle assessment (LCA). An LCA measures the impacts on the environment associated with the life cycle of a product, process, or service. In the past years various studies assessed the environmental impact of biobased products using an LCA. For instance, the review of Walker and Rothman (2020) shows that 56 studies have performed an environmental LCA on biobased polymers. In the past fifteen years, several attempts have been made to integrate social externalities (e.g. child labour) into a life cycle assessment, the so-called social life cycle assessment (Petti et al., 2018).

3.1.3 Monetize externalities

The monetization of externalities involves the valuation of the externalities in monetary terms. By expressing the externalities in monetary terms, the economic outcomes can be compared by organizations. Monetization allows externalities to be taken into account in decision-making, because, when expressed in economic terms, they are dealt with using a language familiar to managers (Eidelwein et al., 2018). There are various valuation approaches to monetize the externalities, of which the damage cost approach and abatement cost approach are the most commonly adopted ones (Amadei et al., 2021). Damage costs are the estimated cost of all economic damage that result from negative externalities (Amadei et al., 2021). For example, emissions of particulate matter harms human health by causing respiratory problems. Damage costs reflect the costs of these emissions to society. Abatement costs is a proxy of the costs for preventing that damage occurs to society (Amadei et al., 2021), for instance the costs for preventing the emissions of greenhouse gas emissions. They indicate how much it is worth to society today to avoid the damage that is projected for the future. Currently, there is a lack of consensus about which valuation method should be used (Amadei et al., 2021). For instance, De Bruyn et al. (2018) and True Cost Initiative (2022) use the abatement cost approach to monetize climate change, while the damage cost approach is used by the Schneider-Marín and Lang (2020).

3.2 Social externalities

Socio-economic externalities (effects on social capital) take the form of human rights violations like child labour, insufficient remuneration, forced labour, gender-based violation and harassment, discrimination, poor working conditions, etc. UNEP has developed a social life cycle assessment (s-LCA), which evaluates the social and economic negative impacts and benefits in decision-making processes towards more sustainable products throughout their life cycle. The guidelines in social LCA have been established by UNEP (2016). Social life cycle assessment is the most recent and least-developed LCA among all other dimensions (environmental and economic) of LCA. There are also other methods to quantify social externalities. For instance, the True Cost Initiative (2022)

developed a true cost accounting method that includes working conditions, gender inequality and human rights violation. Considering the historical evolution of s-LCA, four stages can be distinguished (Ramos Huarachi et al., 2020). S-LCA is currently in stage 'search for standardization' (2017-onward). According to these authors there is still a long way to reach scientific maturity.

Social externalities refer to the positive or negative consequences of an economic activity on social capital and on the quality of life of another (Costanza et al., 2007). Examples of social externalities are child labour, insufficient remuneration, forced labour, gender-based violation and harassment, discrimination, and poor working conditions.

Table 5 provides a longlist of social externalities, which is derived from Benoit and Mazijn (2020). In this study, five different stakeholder categories are distinguished, namely worker, local community, value chain actors (not including consumers), consumer, society, and children.

The s-LCA method of UNEP (2016) does not include a monetization step. Van der Velden and Vogtländer (2017) extended the s-LCA method by including this step in their approach. These authors applied this method to calculate the external costs of clothing production. Five indicators were considered, namely minimum acceptable wage, child labour, extreme poverty, excessive working hours and occupational safety and health. The data was collected at the factory and was based on the actual situation. The costs were based on the salaries per working hours, the working condition, and the required time to make a product. There are only few other methods available to quantify and monetize social externalities. For instance, the True Cost Initiative (2022) and Galgani et al. (2021) developed true cost accounting methods that include various social externalities, such as working remuneration, working conditions, gender inequality and human rights violation. In the study of True Cost Initiative (2022), the costs of worker remuneration is based on the difference between the living wage and the actual remuneration (earnings during a standard work week). Some databases exist to quantify and monetize social externalities, such as the social hotspot database and the s-LCA database (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012; Simapro, 2023).

Table 5 Overview of social externalities, obtained from Benoit and Mazijn (2020)

Stakeholder category	Externality
Worker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freedom of association and collective bargaining Child labor Fair salary Working hours Forced labor Equal opportunities/discrimination Health and safety (worker) Social benefits
Consumer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback mechanism End of life responsibility Health and safety (Netherlands Authority for Consumers & Markets) Consumer privacy Transparency
Local community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to material resources (local) Access to immaterial resources (local) Delocalization and migration Cultural heritage Local employment Safe and healthy living conditions (local community) Respect of indigenous rights Community engagement Secure living conditions
Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology development Public commitment to sustainability issues Contribution to economic development Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts Supplier relationships Fair competition Promoting social responsibility Respect of intellectual property rights

3.3 Environmental externalities and their internalisation

Environmental externalities refer to the effects on natural capital and take the form of greenhouse gas emissions, water, air, and soil pollution, or land-use change, among others, and can have a direct negative impact on climate change, human health, ecosystems and biodiversity as long-term effects (TEEB, 2018). The environmental sustainability of a good, process or service can be evaluated via an LCA. The framework of Environmental externalities occur when environmental impacts of production and consumption activities generate benefits (positive externalities) or costs

(negative externalities) not compensated for by other parties (Eidelwein et al., 2018). The environmental sustainability of a good, process or service can be quantified via an environmental LCA. The framework of environmental LCA is designed within the International Standards Organization (ISO) with reference to ISO standard 14040. Environmental LCA is a widely used method to assess the environmental impact of a (biobased) product. For instance, Spierling et al. (2018) identified 29 studies that used LCA to analyse the environmental sustainability of biobased plastics. A shortcoming of the LCA method is that it considers only negative impacts on the environment (environmental costs), thus ignoring positive impacts (environmental benefits) (Van Linden et al., 2022). For instance, LCA does not consider the positive impact of agricultural production on ecosystem services. Van Linden et al. (2022) propose a new method to assess the sustainability of food products, which takes into account the positive impact of farm production systems on ecosystem services. In their method, they extended the LCA method by including these ecosystem services in their assessment. The authors selected relevant ecosystem services, evaluated these services produced by the agricultural systems under consideration (conventional and organic), and allocated these services to the products delivered by the system. This method is relatively new and does not yet reach scientific maturity. Future research is therefore needed to assess how this new method can be further integrated into LCA, and how these positive environmental impacts should be valued.

Within LCA, various impact assessment methods have been developed such as the ReCiPe method and the product environmental Footprint (PEF) method, which is developed by the European Commission. Each method has a different set of impact categories, each covering a single environmental problem (e.g. climate change or acidification). The PEF considers 16 impact categories, while ReCiPe considers 17 impact categories. Indicators are selected for each category to assess the environmental impact of a product or process. In ReCiPe, midpoint indicators are converted to endpoint indicators, which show the environmental impact on three higher aggregation levels, being 1) effect on human health 2) biodiversity and 3) resource scarcity. In this project, we refer to impact categories as environmental externalities. The impact categories of PEF are provided in Table 6 and used as a starting point in this project. In order to quantify environmental externalities, various LCA databases have been developed, particularly for the agriculture and/or food sector Agri-footprint and Agribalyse are available.

In past years, various methods have been developed to assess the costs associated with environmental externalities. Amadei et al. (2021) reviewed the monetary valuation in life cycle assessment and concluded that the availability of monetary valuation coefficients varies considerably across externalities. Some categories have been studied extensively (e.g. climate change) while others are not (e.g. land use). Different valuation methods are applied in the existing studies, which makes the monetary valuation coefficient of an externality not comparable. Even when the same valuation method is applied, the results show large variability, ranging between one and three orders of magnitude (Amadei et al., 2021). There are a few studies that calculate environmental costs at a higher level (e.g., firm level, plant level or national level), while others did this to determine these costs per product. For instance, Schucht et al. (2021) assessed the environmental costs of air pollution from industrial facilities in the period 2008-2017. Nguyen et al. (2012) analysed the environmental costs of pork meat.

Table 6 List of environmental externalities, derived from European Commission (2021)

Environmental externality
Climate change
Ozone depletion
Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water
Human toxicity – cancer effects
Human toxicity non-cancer effects
Particulate matter
Ionizing radiation – human health effects
Photochemical ozone formation
Acidification
Eutrophication – terrestrial
Eutrophication aquatic
Resource depletion – water
Resource depletion – mineral, fossil
Land transformation

4. Adaptation of CBA for the assessment of sustainability certification in bio-based value chains

In this Section we will align the direct and indirect costs and benefits of certification with the findings from Section 3 that addresses internalisation of external costs and benefits of certification and specifically investigates monetisation. Next, we align it with bio-based value chains and with the practice of certification bodies. Materials in Annex: Supplementary materials are also used in this alignment.

The method of UNEP and RVO are specifically designed for sustainability certification but does not incorporate externalities in their methodology. Hence, it does not make distinction between private costs and external costs. Therefore, we had to extend the method of UNEP and RVO by including external costs and benefits in our method. Table 7 presented below extends its previous version in Section 2 (Table 1) with external costs and benefits which are also the internalised externalities.

The table also elaborates on the possible sources of evidence useful for the following up data collection process. Similar approach to literature search as applied in this document can be used. Search engines like google, google scholar, ScienceDirect, Evidensia database are to be approached for articles, reports, and grey literature.

Table 7 Extended cost typology with internalised externalities and indication for data collection

Item	Internal /External	Direct /Indirect	Item	Description	Possible sources of information for data collection
Costs	Internal	Direct	Auditing costs	Costs that a company has to pay for an external audit to become or remain certified	Auditing costs will be collected from auditors, literature such as Van Dam et al. (2012). See also Table A. 1 and Table A. 2
			Certification fees	Membership fee and/or quantity-dependent fee	Certification fees will be collected from the documentation of certification schemes. See Table 2 and Table A. 5 for an example for FSC.
		Indirect	Administrative indirect costs	Adapting the company or farm administration to adequate traceability tools and systems and man-days to ensure the correct (and documented) implementation of the chain of custody	Administrative indirect costs will be collected from auditors and case study/pilot participants, literature such as Van Dam et al. (2012)
			Indirect costs related to sustainability compliance, including training	Investments for adapting production and trade processes to the requirements of sustainability standards, training of workers in sustainable agriculture technologies and processes etc..	Indirect costs related to sustainability compliance will be collected from case studies such as those presented in Section 2.1 and using interviews. Evidensia database is to be consulted.
	External	n.a.	Environmental	Environmental costs (e.g. from pollution) arising from the production or consumption of a good or service	Will be collected from literature and biobased value chain members if they are quantified. Evidensia database is to be consulted.
		n.a.	Social	Costs arising from the production or consumption of a good or service (e.g. child labour)	Costs related to negative social impacts are difficult to quantify and interviews, case studies need to be searched for.
Benefits	Internal	Direct	Efficiency management improvements and/or within company	Benefits related to reduction in the use of inputs, such as water, fertilizers and energy	Benefits from efficiency and or management improvements will be collected from specific cases. Guidance from Table A. 3 can be used.
		Direct	Price premium	Additional revenues obtained by selling the certified product	Market data on prices for certified and non-certified products
		Indirect	Improved market position	Image and branding, meeting demands of the market	Image and branding, legal compliance. Information will be based on expert estimation and/or interviews

Item	Internal /External	Direct /Indirect	Item	Description	Possible sources of information for data collection
	External	n.a.	Environmental	Environmental external benefits arising from producing and/or consuming the certified product	Will be collected from literature and/or biobased value chain members if they are quantified. Evidensia database is to be consulted.
		n.a.	Social	Social external benefits arising from producing and/or consuming the certified good or product	Will be collected from literature and/or biobased value chain members if they are quantified. Evidensia database is to be consulted.

Source: own presentation.

5. Conclusions and discussion on methodological challenges

While several studies identify effects (or impacts) of certification schemes, there are too few studies that value such effects. The complexity of the evaluation (or monetization) has also been presented in Section 3. Table 7 above reflects on the possible sources of data needed for a cost-benefits analysis of a certification scheme implementation. Example studies are found among the cases presented in Van Dam et al. (2012) and UNEP (2016). Table A. 5 in Annex presents an example of cost categories for the sector of forestry, while similar example is also available for the sector of agriculture (not specifically for any product).

Prior to providing further recommendations for the data collection, which will be carried out further in the project (D4.3 “Data collection template for cost benefit analysis”), we first recap on the findings from the literature.

While the private costs of certification, like certification fees, can be found in the documentation of certification schemes, the costs of audit are already more case-study specific, depending on various factors and will need more efforts for quantification.

The review studies by Malek and Abdul Rahim (2022) and Tröster and Hiete (2018), who performed a thematic review of forest certification publications concluded that in terms of the most researched forest certification scheme, the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) were the two schemes mentioned most often in the studies. These certification schemes would therefore provide enough evidence for the potential cost-benefit analysis. The next challenge is in the quantification of effects. Although the existing literature may demonstrate the effects of certification schemes, the sector coverage may be a challenging aspect when addressing bio-based products.

It is important to stipulate that the data collection will be driven by the value chain selected, i.e., the combination of a “bio-based product type x certification scheme x supply chain characteristics”. For these, the deliverables on the findings from the relevant project deliverables are to be consulted:

- Sector/ bio-based product (link to Deliverable 1.1)
- Certification system (link Deliverable 1.2)
- Value chain and type of product: raw material, intermediate product scope 1 - 2- 3, or final product (link to Deliverable 2.1).

It is also expected that finding the data and especially those on external costs and benefits will be very difficult. To deal with the data challenge of finding the right data, Evidensia database as well as studies on the level of assurance of certification schemes and on the external drives of certification for its adoption (or its barrier) will be of use. Discussion in Section 2.4 refers to a possibility to assess costs and benefits through factors that may influence these.

6. Next steps

Having outlined the methodology and the main challenges to address, the following next steps are to be taken towards costs-benefit analysis of selected bio-based supply chains:

1. Provide an overview of the three promising value chains selected from different industrial sectors (textile, chemical, wood) coupled with their suitable certification schemes for the CBA. Deliverable 4.2 “Selection of biobased value chains for cost benefit analysis” provides an
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overview of different option for further selection of the value chains per textile, chemical and wood sector.

2. Development of the data collection template (Deliverable 4.3 “Data collection template for cost benefit analysis”), where the identified costs and benefits to carry out CBA for the certification schemes will be specified along the selected value chains. In other words, a data search will be performed to retrieve a quantifiable information for CBA on value chains described in Section 3 of Deliverable 4.2. The template will be developed with the needs of the specific value chains in mind and will draw from the experience of Control Union with other templates that derive data from certified companies, with additional questions relevant to add to the CBA.
 3. The development of the data templates will be done for the three chains in a sequential way to achieve continuous integration of the learnings and thus in improvements. The development of the first data collection template will be tailored to one of the certification schemes for which sufficient input from the existing literature is available. The best-in-class scheme will be considered for the third assessment.
 4. Collection of data for the selected biobased value will take place in Task 4.4 thereafter and will be presented in Deliverable 4.4 “Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains”. The data search will start from desk study guided by Table 7 from this deliverable for the specified certification schemes and value chains. Specific literature search on costs and benefits of certification schemes applicable to selected value chains from the sector of textile, chemical and wood will be performed. Further, this search will be enriched with interviews from chains partners.
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Annex: Supplementary materials

Table A. 1 Certification audit fee per ISH based on SPOC with 500 ISHs

Cost items	Unit	Certification audit	Surveillance audit
Number of auditors	persons	2	
Number of ISH in SPOC	ISH/SPOC	500	
Audit cost	USD/day	358.00	
Accommodation	USD/day	47.73	
Audit Cost			
Stage 1	day	6	12
Stage 2	day	12	–
Stakeholder consultation	day	1	1
Total	day	19	13
	USD	6801.91	4653.94
Additional Cost			
Accommodation for 2 auditors	day	20 (10 days/auditor)	14 (7 days/auditor)
	USD	954.65	668.26
Transportation	USD	715.99	715.99
Total cost	USD	8472.55	6038.19
Cost per ISH	USD/ISH	16.95	12.08

Source: Van Dam et al. (2012)

Table A. 2 Indicative number of man-days needed for situation that 10 farmers, grouped under one legal entity and, a storage facility (also grouped FGP under some systems) are audited

	Farmers + Gathering Point	First Farmers individual + storage	Farmers multi-site + storage unit
RSB	-	10*4 days + 2 days = 42 days	3.2*4 days + 2 days = 14 days
RSPO	20 (indicative)	n.a.	n.a.
RTRS	-	10* 3 days+ 2 days = 32 days	3.2*3 days + 2 days = 11 days
Bonsucro	15 (indicative)	n.a.	n.a.
ISCC	-	10* 3 days+ 2 days = 32 days	3.3*3 days = 10 days
NTA8080	-	10* 3 days+ 2 days = 32 days	3.2*3 days + 5 additional days + 2 days = 16 days
2BSvs	2 (1 to 3) ^[1]	n.a.	n.a.
EDcertR	Indicative: 3-4 farmers/day (excl FGP)	n.a.	n.a.

Source: Van Dam et al. (2012)

Table A. 3 Overview of realised early benefits of using sustainability standards

CLUSTER	Early Benefit	Specific benefit
OPERATIONS	Operational efficiency & risk management	Improved management systems and processes Improved operational risk management Improved governance & membership engagement Innovation
	Sustainability strategy	Increases awareness on sustainability issues Benchmark or roadmap to operationalise sustainability Helps achieve sustainability / business objectives Improved performance / impact monitoring
	Human capital development	Improved working conditions & worker benefits Employee skill development Employee satisfaction & retention
PROCUREMENT	Supply chain risk management	Improved management and mitigation of risks in supply chains
	Supply chain coordination	More reliable suppliers Improved quality of trading relationships with suppliers (e.g. stability, volumes, payment terms)
	Transparency & traceability	Increased product traceability and transparency
SALES AND MARKETING	Marketing strategy	Facilitates customer communication (e.g. claims) Enables to differentiate from other brands or businesses
	Market access	Client retention, access to new customers and markets (e.g. geographies) Improved quality of trading relationships with customers (e.g. stability, volumes, payment terms)
	Price and premium reward	Additional cash premium or higher prices
STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	Access to finance	Improved investor communications Improved access to finance and more favourable finance conditions
	Public sector engagement	Improved relationships with the government Improved voice in policymaking and public sector investments
	NGO & donor relationships	Improved civil society communication and dialogue Opportunities in partnership building, programme development and access to donor funding

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	Access to knowledge and support	Improved access to information Improved access to capacity building Improved access to inputs
SECTOR-WIDE CHANGE	Sector alignment & Coordination	Networking, learning and dialogue Improved sector-wide alignment on sustainability
	Public policy influence	Public policy dialogue and influence

Source: Molenaar (2022)

Table A. 4 Experiences of the drivers and hindrances in certification processes

Certification Dissonance	Drivers	Hinderances
Company characteristics	Flexibility	Small size Expensive
Customer/market	Positive reputation Competitive advantages Expansion	Greenwashing No market changes Personal relations
Certification scheme	Trust Internal routines Quality mark	Rigid rules/bureaucracy Being controlled No difference on green practice Internal motivation
Emotions	Pride/identity Enthusiasm	Anger/frustration Discouragement/resignation

Source: Flagstad et al. (2022)

Annex 2 AAF Calculation Tables for COC certification

1. The following steps and table shall be applicable to the determination of AAF chargeable on COC certification (for single site certification omit steps a and b):

- a) Determine the exact Forest Products Turnover of each individual site.
- b) Calculate the aggregated Forest Products Turnover for all sites by adding together the values in step a.
- c) Look up the AAF Class and AAF Class Minimum Turnover in Table 2 below, according to the Forest Products Turnover (Column 2). For example, AAF Class Minimum Turnover for Class 1 is '0', for Class 2 is 1 Million USD and so on.
- d) Derive the Excess Turnover as follows:

$$\text{Excess Turnover} = \text{Forest Products Turnover} - \text{AAF Class Minimum Turnover}$$

- e) Look up the Base Fee and Variable Fee in Table 2 below according to whether the certification is for a Processor or Trader.
- f) Use the Base Fee, Variable Fee and Excess Turnover values to calculate the final AAF using the following formula:

$$\text{AAF} = \text{Base Fee} + \left(\frac{\text{Excess Turnover}}{\$1,000,000} \times \text{Variable Fee} \right)$$

NOTE: The value of \$1,000,000 in the formula is a fixed number applicable to all AAF Classes and is not linked to the AAF Class Minimum Turnover.

- g) Round up the final AAF amount to the nearest USD. If this final amount is below the Minimum AAF specified below in clause 2 then the Minimum AAF figure will be charged.

Table 2. AAF for Processor and Trader certification (in USD). Variable fees charged per USD 1 million in Forest Products Turnover above the minimum within that Class.

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6
Class	Forest Products Turnover	Processor Base (USD)	Processor Variable (USD)	Trader Base (USD)	Trader Variable (USD)
Class 1	0 – 1 Million	0.00	568.70	0.00	170.61
Class 2	> 1 – 5 Million	569.00	186.12	171.00	55.84
Class 3	> 5 – 25 Million	1,314.00	77.55	395.00	23.27
Class 4	> 25 – 100 Million	2,865.00	31.02	861.00	9.31
Class 5	> 100 – 500 Million	5,192.00	18.61	1,560.00	5.58
Class 6	> 500 – 2,000 Million	12,636.00	15.51	3,792.00	4.65
Class 7	> 2,000 Million	35,901.00	12.93	10,767.00	3.88

Figure A 1. Annual fee calculation for chain of custody for FSC certification
(Source, FSC, 2022)

Table A. 5 Example of costs and benefits for Forestry sector as presented in the UNEP methodology

Investment and operating costs			Added benefits								Avoided costs																																																			
Private		Public	Economic				Social		Environmental		Economic				Social		Environmental																																													
Capital and management	Training		Audit	Direct		Indirect		Direct	indirect	Direct	Indirect	Direct		Indirect		Direct	indirect	Direct	indirect																																											
			Private	Public	Private	Public	Private					Public	Private	Public	Private					Public	Private	Public																																								
Establishment/Expansion of Forest Protected Areas, including enforcement costs (US\$/year). Costs associated with the respect of legal and customary rights of indigenous people (US\$/ha). Sustainable plantations (US\$/ha).			Operation & Management Costs (US\$/ha). Labor cost (US\$/person; US\$/year; US\$/ton).			Training and supervision of forest workers (US\$/person).			Initial and annual audit costs (US\$/ha). Compliance costs, e.g. retaining a percentage of trees to function for wildlife habitat.			Subsidy to family forest owners to support costs of certification audits (US\$/ha). Subsidies to local forest communities (US\$/year). Development and implementation of policies for Environmental.			Increased access to global BioTrade markets (% or US\$/year). Increased productivity (US\$/ha). Premium market price (%; US\$/ton).			Increased revenues from taxes on forestry as result of increased private profits (US\$/year). Revenue from selling forest credits (US\$/ton).			Additional revenues from improved corporate reputation/customer loyalty (US\$/year). Increased revenues in other sectors, e.g. eco-tourism, agriculture etc., as result of reduced environmental impact (US\$/year).			Additional fiscal space to support and promote sustainable forest management (US\$/year).			Increased income of local forest communities (US\$/year).			Increased access of forest dwellers to traditional forest products (%).			Increase in forest cover from sustainable plantation (forest cover as % of total land).			Improved air quality (Air Quality Index). Preservation of biodiversity (GEF biodiversity index).			Reduced pesticides use (US\$/year). Reduced losses of timber and non-timber (US\$/year).			Avoided costs of reforestation programmes (US\$/year).			Reduced economic losses in other sectors, e.g. eco-tourism, as result of environmental degradation (US\$/year).			Avoided costs of imports of timber and non-timber forest products (US\$/year).			Avoided loss of habitat by forest dwellers (households/year). Reduced damages from floods and inundations on households (US\$/year).			Reduced costs of urbanization from abandoned forests, e.g. subsidies to urban poor (US\$/year). Reduced health costs from air pollution, floods etc. (number of hospitalized people/year).			Reduced deforestation (forest cover as % of total land). Reduced costs of desertification of forest area (Aridity Index, Rain concentration index).			Reduced costs of replacement of ecosystem services, e.g. watershed management (US\$/year).		

Source: UNEP (2016).

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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